

Analysis of Linguistic and Cultural Units Related to Occupational Names

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Abstract:

Linguistic and cultural units related to professional names are highlighted in the article based on evidence.

Keywords: occupation, craft, linguoculterema, oikonym, geonym, anthroponym, onomastics, onomastic conversion, etc.

Every aspect of a nation's culture is reflected in its language, which is the main tool for passing down national values to future generations. Language performs the task of preserving cultural symbols and conveying them to the next generation, as a means of expressing the national mentality, it embodies the world view based on national values.

In the field of linguistic culture, which analyzes the relationship between language and culture, the level of expression of cultural views in the language, national-cultural, ancient and modern views of the peoples of the world, customs, traditions, and the characteristics of the expression of values in a specific folk speech are analyzed.

Lingvokulterema was introduced to science by the Russian linguist V.V. Vorobyov. *Lingvokulterema* is an interlevel complex unit, which in its content represents a dialectical unit of linguistic and non-linguistic (conceptual or object) meaning. The scientist explains *lingvokulterema* as a sum of forms of language signs, their content and cultural meaning. Of course, this opinion is valid. In the Uzbek language culture, linguocultural terms related to profession have also been formed. They are the views, attention, respect and attitude of the Uzbek people to the profession and its owners. is a product.

Lingvokul t e rema _ in some literature, they are also called *linguistic and cultural units* . Linguistic units consisting of a combination of linguistic and cultural content, in the semantics of which cultural

information is evident, are considered linguistic and cultural units . Usually, linguistic and cultural units include phraseologisms, standards, symbols, metaphors, static similes, speech labels, words related to traditions and rituals, riddles, national realities, archetypes, mythologies, lacunae, precedent units, etc.¹

The need for a person to learn a certain profession, to raise an honest family by doing it, is also emphasized in Islamic sources. Religious scholars say: "Four things are evidence of happiness: correct speech, modesty, work in an honest profession, keeping a secret." Our faith-believing people certainly appreciate such high human qualities and follow them, and raise their children in the same spirit.

It is worth noting that to be engaged in a certain craft is a legacy to us from the prophets and sages. There is such a hadith: "Whoever Allah keeps as a friend, He makes people need him." A person can achieve great rewards during his life only by honest work. The Messenger of Allah, may God bless him and grant him peace, said in one of his hadiths: "Surely, Allah loves a believer who is a craftsman."

It is known from history that Adam was a farmer; Nuh alayhissalam carpentry; David, who was both a king and a prophet, blacksmithing; Idris alayhissalam calligraphy; The Lord of the Universe Muhammad, may God bless him and grant him peace, raised sheep and was engaged in trade in his youth.

Hazrat Imam Azam, the founder of our sect, was engaged in gas sales, and Khoja Ahmed Yassavi was engaged in farming. Sheikh Ibrahim Ajari was a bricklayer. Hazrat Farabi, who earned the name "Arastus of the East", was a farmer, Abu Ali Ibn Sina was a mediciner, Sheikhu Mashaihu Abu Sayyid Harros was a shoemaker, poet Sakkaki was a knife maker, and Sheikh Abul Abbas Amili was a butcher. Sheikh Abul Hasan was a jeweler, Sheikh Khoja Banan was a porter, Muhaddis Muslim ibn Hajjaj was a merchant, Khoja Bahauddin Naqshband was a painter, Imam Ghazali was a yarn spinner, and poet Zavqi was a Mahsidist.²

Since time immemorial, the Uzbek people have honored and honored the profession. In the proverbs, "... all virtues, philosophy, outlook of the Uzbek, his attitude to various life situations³, including his attitude to professions, are vividly expressed.

Mahmud Koshgari's work "Devonu Lug'otit Turk" says in an ancient proverb, "*Erdamsiz dan qut chertilur*" , that is, "*Happiness and state will go away from a person without skills and manners*".⁴

In our people, who lived in tribal or clan relations and engaged in a certain profession since time immemorial, proverbs appeared on the topic of labor and work, including professions, in which the profession was considered the basis of beauty, abundance and endurance of life: "*Having a profession means happiness.*" , "*A person who respects his profession is enough for his admirer*" , "*A craftsman is sympathetic*" , "*Society is decorated with handicrafts*" .⁵

One of the best examples of Uzbek linguo-cultural themes is "*Craft you learn diligently, Make a living from your craft*" , "*Craft will feed you, ride a horse, wear a coat*" , "*Profession, the bottom of the profession is destiny*" , "*Craft is a flowing spring, Knowledge is a burning lamp*" , "*Craftsman*" a young man is a fruit tree" , "*Craft is an inexhaustible treasure*" , "*Having a craft is owning a mine*" , "*Every craft has its essence*" , "*Craft, get your livelihood from craft*" , "*Craft and knowledge are property*" , "*Craft also makes iron*" A series of folk proverbs such as "*The craftsman's bread is full*"

¹Look. Khudoyberganova D. A brief explanatory dictionary of linguistic and cultural terms. - Tashkent: Turon zamin ziya, 2015. - B.26.

²Umarov S. The hardest profession // [http // Muslim . en](http://Muslim.en)

³Madayev O., Sobitova T. Folk oral poetic creation. - Tashkent : Sharq, 2003. - P. 11.

⁴Koshgari, Mahmoud. The dictionary is Turkish. - Tashkent: Science, 1963. - vol. II. - B. 266.

⁵Matlabbeka Ulugbek's daughter. A bouquet of proverbs. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1994. - 128 p.

and "The craftsman creates destiny with his profession" show the greatness of the craft, its essence and importance in human social life, the craft is one of the material and spiritual bases of life, the craftsman, that is, in the life of the owners of various crafts. It is said that it is the destiny of their profession to live well, full, and well.⁶

"If you're a farmer, be at the head of the land, if you're a soldier, be with the people" and his proverb "If you're a farmer, be at the edge, if you're a shepherd - with him", "If you're a farmer, be in the fields, if you're a fisherman, be in the water" not only in options farmer, soldier, shepherd, fisherman, in general, every profession owner should be at his place of work, care about the development and improvement of his profession, work diligently, and be in harmony with the country with his profession.⁷

In the literary culture of the Uzbek people, it has long been said that the work of a farmer is hard, laborious and honorable, he is valued and honored as the owner of a profession that creates sustenance and gives life to people. This is clearly reflected in the following folk proverbs: " **The farmer's working hours are countless**", " **The farmer's bread is in the field**", " **Man's livelihood is in the hands of the farmer** ",

" **The farmer is the captain of food**", " **The farmer is the jeweler of the land**", "The tables were filled with the generosity of **the farmer's hand**" .

" **One today of a herdsman is two of tomorrow**" it is said that the animals that shepherds and herdsmen feed and take care of will multiply tomorrow and satisfy people's need for food, especially meat products.

In some folk proverbs, a comparison is made about the complexity of the professions of *farmers and shepherds* :

The farmer earns if it rains,

The shepherd dies.

Option:

When the farmer sleeps,

Ch o ' pon dies .

Proverbs are about the tireless work of a shepherd and a farmer, and it is said that after the farmer harvests what he sowed in the spring in the fall, he rests for a while until the next spring, but the shepherd does not rest even in the four seasons of the year. In another proverb, the owners of both professions are glorified as the sultan and king of the place where they work: " **The farmer is the sultan of the land, The shepherd is the ruler of the pasture.**"⁸

"Carpentry is not a monkey's work", the fact that mastery is not a profession for everyone is conveyed by means of the metaphor of a monkey. According to folk tales, including Alisher Navoi's story "The Monkey and the Carpenter", the monkey lost his tail because he wanted to become a carpenter. In this proverb, it is said that if you don't see a master, don't study, don't try every profession, you won't learn, you will suffer.

"A jeweler knows the value of gold", "A jeweler knows the value of gold, what does a plumber know?!", "A husband knows the value of a husband, A jeweler knows the value of gold"; A nation with many options, such as "A jeweler knows the value of gold, Zabarjad - a merchant." in proverbs

⁶Look. Shomaksudov Sh., Shorahmedov Sh. A storehouse of meanings. - Tashkent: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2001. - B. 439.

⁷Look. Shomaksudov Sh., Shorahmedov Sh. The same work, p. 78.

⁸Uzbek folk proverbs. Collectors: T. Mirzaev, B. Sarimsakov, A. Musogulov. - Tashkent: Literature and Art Publishing House, 1989. - 512 p.

while It is a wise idea that people who are not directly related to it do not know the value of everything, heavy-light, low-high and good-bad. Also, the proverb can be understood in the correct sense as "Only a jeweler knows the value and value of gold and jewelry."

In our opinion, every profession has its own merits and wisdom. The trouble is that there is no easy, light profession. Any profession is achieved through research, study, years of love and professional skill and improvement. In many folk proverbs, the same aspect is expressed figuratively, similes, comparisons, metaphors: "Every profession has a sign", " **An artist can show the soul in a picture** ." ⁹, " **The artist brings light to the hearts**", " **The potter can create a miracle from ordinary clay**", " **The wrinkles of the potter 's hand are the heaven of angels**", " **The worker is as refined as the metals he uses**", " **The work of the worker is the power of the country**", "The key to the treasure of health" - **in the doctor**", " **The doctor's conscience is the patient's medicine**", " **The surgeon's slaughter - revives**", " **The doctor is the keeper of the doors of entry and exit into the world** " .

" A good **cook is a doctor**", referring to the fact that delicious, sweet food gives strength and healing to a person, a cook who cooks such dishes is compared to a doctor.

In the Uzbek linguistic culture, certain professions, including craftsmen, are honored with special respect, and the proverb "A craftsman is a god" is a clear proof of this. In this proverb, which was formed on the basis of the traditions of the Islamic religion specific to our people, the farmer is highly valued as *the friend of God* . First of all, the glorification of a craftsman who sews, mends, and mends shoes: boots, shoes, etc., is unique to the Eastern, including Uzbek, linguistic culture.

Secondly, the proverb expresses a high recognition of the profession as an honest, hard-working profession, which is necessary for everyone. It should be noted that we did not observe such an assessment given to any other profession in the process of analysis.

Traditions, along with being present in all areas of social life, also cover the process of origin. Tradition expresses people's relationship to things and objects, to nature. It is known that there are no traditions in art and literature, in military teams and universities, in sports and industrial teams, but there are traditions. For example, taking the oath of servicemen who joined the army and students who entered the higher education institution, raising the country's flag in honor of the winning athlete at major sports competitions, and playing the national anthem are traditions. Tradition is a set of rules and regulations that are embedded in people's minds and accepted by the general or a certain group as a social and cultural phenomenon that arises on the basis of natural and social needs in the course of historical development, is inherited from generation to generation, and affects the spiritual life of people.

Similar traditions exist in the field of vocational learning and training: our ancestors, following the traditions of proverbs such as "A young man has forty skills", "A young man has seventy skills", "A young man has seventy skills", taught his children, especially who paid serious attention to teaching their sons various trades at a young age, tried to raise their children in the spirit of valuing and honoring their father's profession. Proverbs such as ¹⁰" *Father's profession is the state's profession*", "Father's profession is honest to the son", "Father's profession fills the stomach", "Father's profession is an inheritance for the child", "He who takes up his father's profession is not to be despised", "He who abandoned his father's profession is incorrigible" is also a proof of this.

Not only in proverbs, but also in the works of great scholars, scientists and writers, there are ideas describing the profession that have become wisdom. Hazrat Ali says: "Craft is a person's wealth" and highly appreciates the position of craft in human social life ¹¹.

⁹Matlabbeka Ulugbek's daughter. A bouquet of proverbs. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1994. - B. 30-31.

¹⁰Look. Shomaksudov Sh., Shorahmedov Sh. That work, p. 440.

¹¹Alisher Navoi. Nazm ul is a jewel. - Tashkent: Akademnashr, 2016. - B. 66.

Allama Mahmud Zamakhshari's work "Nice Expressions" says, "*There are many artisans, but there are few skilled ones (that is, there are many masters, few masters)*".

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